

Title: Big Data in Insurance Industry, Challenges and Opportunities

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INTRODUCTION:

Big data era has had a tremendous impact on insurance industry. Insurance industry works based on assessment of risk for each policy holder. Abundance of generated and stored data helps to estimate the risk more accurately which could benefit both carriers and policy holders. However, when it comes to the practice, there are some obstacles. This presentation will cover application of big data in insurance industry and challenges insurance companies experience using big data.

AIM:

To discuss new type of data and analytic approaches which can be incorporated with traditional insurance risk assessments methods and learn what are the limitation, challenges, and advantages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Presentation will cover emerging methods of advance analytics in all lines of insurance such as behavior based developed scoring system, incorporating medical science with demographic data to improve underwriting models, role of telematic devices in real time monitoring of customers.

RESULTS:

Benefits and limitations of incorporating big data and advanced data science techniques in a few specific insurance applications will be discussed.

CONCLUSIONS:

While big data and advanced analytic tools create lots of opportunity in this industry, it created new challenges for carriers. Strict and inconsistent regulations, data ownership issue, need for heavy investment on anti-fraud and data leakage solutions, sustainability, and disruption of existing models are examples of these issues.

KEYWORDS:

Big Data; Predictive Analytic; Insurance, Risk

BIOGRAPHY:

Dr. Sara Aby is the lead Data Scientist with Perr&Knight. Sara earned her Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering. Sara has more than ten years of experience in various fields of computational advanced data analytics and data science methodologies. She applied predictive modeling techniques in various industries such as insurance, banking, fraud, digital devices and biological data.

Sara is a former National Science Foundation (NSF) Open Science Data Cloud PIRE fellow. She co-authored a book published by CRC Press that includes predictive analytics. Sara has been awarded multiple prestigious academic fellowships and scholarships. She earned multiple certifications in predictive modeling, fraud detection, credit reporting, statistics, finance and banking.